

Culture, Ethnicity And National Integration: The Nigerian Experience

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Abstract

This paper x-rays culture as the way by which people in the society behave. It looked at conceptual clarification of culture, ethnicity and national integration in Nigeria. It also examines the components of culture as the basis for societal development and the basic functions of culture in the society. The paper is of the opinion that culture of a society includes everything in the life of its members which they learn through direct or indirect contact with other people. The paper also examines causes of ethnic conflicts in Nigeria and its effects in Nigeria society. It sees ethnicity as principally a social phenomenon that is rooted in people's persistent way of life particularly the long shared tradition. The paper also looked at the indices for measuring national integration, efforts made by federal government of Nigeria to achieve national integration and factors impeding the success of national integration in Nigeria. It highlights the role of culture and ethnicity in promoting national integration in Nigeria. The paper concludes by making useful contributions that will help Nigeria to overcome the challenges posed by culture and ethnic consciousness. Recommendations were made which will help Nigeria to achieve national integration.

Keyword: Culture, Ethnicity, National Integration.

Introduction

Nigeria is heterogeneous society with multifarious and divergent ethnic and cultural groups. It has about six hundred and nineteen ethnic nationalities. The fact that these nationalities were brought together to form the Nigerian state without their consent by the British has remained a major problem in the quest for national integration amid ethnic and

cultural pluralism that informed the idea of federal system of government in Nigeria. It will be difficult for people of different customs, traditions and culture to stay together in a unitary system of government without chaos and disintegration. Federalism has therefore been adjudged to be the best option for Nigeria to maintain and preserve their cultural values and identities as means of achieving national integration. As observed by Atoukudu (2015),

federalism is a veritable protection against the problems associated with ethnicity and cultural diversity especially the fears associated with minorities and other ethnically disadvantaged groups within a country of multiple nationalities. National integration is easily achieved among the federating ethnic and cultural units through federalism. Studies have shown that while culture and ethnicity aid national integration by serving as mechanisms of resocialization, they at the same time encourage divisive tendencies among citizens of any nation. For most countries, the major impediments to the process of national integration are cultural differences and ethnicity. Integrating the heterogeneous cultural and ethnic groups in a nation is not often a very easy exercise as these groups often see themselves as competitors not partners and this makes the problem a complex one (Obi, 2006). It is regrettable to note that Nigeria is currently confronted with the challenges of becoming a true and proper nation with citizens that will yield instinctive loyalty to the nation and not only to the ethnic groups, citizens whose loyalty to the Nigerian nation will influence and indeed direct their attitude to work towards national integration and meaningful development (Ikime, 2003). This paper therefore seeks to examine the place of culture and ethnicity in Nigerian search for national integration.

Conceptual Clarification

Culture

Culture occupies an important place in virtually all the fields of human endeavour. Often, we have such expressions as political culture, feeding culture, reading culture, maintenance culture and behavioral culture etc. The versatility of the concept often leads to misconception of the term culture as well as multiplicity of its definitions.

According to Biobaku (1986) cited in Ebirim and Uzoagba (2011) culture is that complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, laws, customs and any other abilities required by man. Unoh (1986) in his own view perceived the term culture as the totality of the material, spiritual, artistic, intellectual and other accomplishments of a people, which gives some indications of their way of life, their mode of existence and the by-products of their type or level of civilization. This definition explains that cultural factors are all inclusive and are found in man's past, present and future life. Further, Defleur (1977) cited in Ebirim and Uzoagba (2011) believes that culture refers to "the totality of all material, social and symbolic creation that a society's members have incorporated into their overall design for living. This implies that culture is historically a derived system of explicit and implicit designs for living which tend to be shared by all members of the society. In explicit culture, the society are aware of issues around them and pattern their behavior in accordance with cultural design or rules, while in implicit culture it involves those aspects of culture which are unknown to people but yet they act on it in their everyday life.

Similarly Okere (2001) defines culture as the total way of life of people in the society. He further explained that the content of culture in the society includes everything in the life of its members which they learn through direct or indirect contact with other people, eg customary ways of behaving in their everyday life, religious belief, moral standard, the way in which their family life is organized, their method of providing food and shelter, language, their government and any form of artistic expression.

Culture from every parameter is one of the indices of any organized human group. It

makes a cultured group to live together and also give the group a distinctive outlook. It is generally believed that without society, there will be no culture. That implies why the environment plays a vital role in the culture of a society. Each society has its own unique culture which has been developed throughout its history and which is passed on from one generation to another. New members born into any society do not inherit their culture biologically but it has to be learned from childhood. This means that everyone born into a particular society will, in the process of growing up, have acquired certain belief, attitudes and patterns of behavior in common with other society which will make them different from people of other society, Ebirim, Emenyonu, Uzoagba (2013).

Ethnicity

Hardly will one find any nation of the world without ethnic groups. What is unpredictable is that there difference in the number of groups that may constitute given country. Many ethnic groups in most nations of the world have features which are applicable to others. Erikson (2002) sees ethnicity as relating to aspects of relationship between groups which consider themselves and are regarded by others, as being culturally distinctive. The idea of ethnicity according to him implies that the culture of one group is different from that of another group. He maintained that there is a hierarchy in ethnic groups within a society, with some groups enjoying more status and greater material rewards than other groups. Similarly, Schacter (2006) defined ethnicity as a group set apart from others because of its national origin or distinction, which culturally one ethnic group must be different of the others. In line with these assertion Mezieobi (2014) opined that ethnicity simply mean a collectivity of persons who are held together by shared cultural traditions or

heritage which reflects on their common ancestry, mother – tongue, language religion etc. this group has a tradition that held then together from time immemorial, they are not disorganized out rightly by acculturation process but can be distinguished from other groups through cultural patterns.

National Integration

In every human society the quest for peace, unity and progress has always been the focal point for every activity. National Integration is described as the bringing together of the various ethnic and social groups into harmonious and working relationship with loyalty to the country placed above other loyalties (Amucheazi, 1998). In the same vein Barker (1998) cited in Uzoagba (2008) describes national integration as a situation where there is a high level of amicable social interaction among various peoples of a nation, and where they are admitted into or deployed in the country's institutions without regard to sex, class or ethnic bias, religious or political learning.

Similarly, Mkpa (1992) perceives national integration as a situation in which the nation's ethnic groups, religious groups, geographical division, political interests and all other geo-political and socio-cultural characteristics translate the nation into an indissoluble fusion. He further states that national integration means a society where co-operation, togetherness, the spirits of patriotism, nationalism and solidarity are predominant. In line with this, Weiner (1967) cited in Uzoagba (2008) conceptualized national integration as the existence of an ethnically plural society in which each group is characterized by its own language or other self-conscious cultural qualities. National integration thus refers specifically to the problem of creating a sense of

territorial nationality which overshadows, eliminates or subordinate parochial loyalties. Weiner went further to demonstrate that integration covers a vast range of human relationship and attitudes. He distinguishes five such areas as, the integration of diverse and discrete cultural loyalties, and the development of a sense of nationality, the integration of political units into a common territorial framework with a government which can exercise authority, the integration of the rulers and the ruled, the integration of the citizens into a common political process, and finally the integration of the individual into organizations for purposive activity.

Component of Culture

Components of culture has been viewed from several angles. Material and non-material cultures are integral parts of the culture of the people as one of the two types is complementary to the other. In line with this, Ogbaru (1922) cited in Schaefer (2006) made a useful distinction between the elements of material and non material culture. According to him material culture refers to the physical or technological aspect of our daily lives, which includes food, houses, factories and raw materials. Non material culture is also referred to as ways of using material objects such as customs, beliefs, philosophies, government and patterns of communication. He further stated that each culture takes into consideration its own distinctive ways of handling basic societal task to be “natural”, but in fact, methods of education, marital ceremonies, religious doctrines, and other aspect of culture are learned and transmitted through human interaction within specific societies.

Similarly Itedjere (1993) cited in Ebirim, Emenyonu and Uzoagba (2013) grouped culture into two major categories, notably, material and

non-material culture. The former are man-made, it can be seen and used to assess man’s level of technological development, they include, house, farming tools, humanity and fighting implements, dresses, cooking utensils and other things which can be seen and touched with hands. While non material culture includes, language, norms, beliefs, peoples taboo and sanction. Material and non-material cultures are integral parts of the culture of the people as one of the two types is complementary to the other, for example; music and musical instrument, agriculture and farming tools.

Furthermore, Mezieobi (1992) viewed components of culture to includes, technological, ideological and organizational components. According to him, technological components of culture are skills, arts, artifacts, roads, bending and bridges and all these technologies and devices are used by the members of the society to perform the tasks that are necessary for the continued existence of the society while mental or ideological components of culture comprises of people belief System, their ideas, values, languages and music. Also organizational components of culture have to do with people’s law and how a group of people coordinates, their behaviours and sanction which has to do with maintenance of law and order.

Functions of Culture in the Society

Culture serves as a “stamp” or “trade mark” that distinguished one society from the other.

Culture integrates, sympathizes and interprets the value institutions and norms of a society as it changes them with meaningful purposes.

Culture functions in the society as the basis for social unity and solidarity. Cultural unity

normally inspires loyalty, patriotism and devotion to duty.

- Culture functions as a corporate entity that relates, coordinates, integrates and above all the repository of peoples social, political, economic heritage and values.
- Culture is the architect and molder of social personality of people in the society.

Causes of Ethnic problems in Nigeria

In Nigeria, it is quite obvious that majority of ethnic groups wants to maintain their status quo in terms of power and authority in dominance, the minority ethnic groups would not rest on their efforts in wanting to be heard on the political table or scene. Problems of ethnicity has continued to generate conflicts, violence and destruction among ethnic groups in Nigeria. According to Mezieobi, Mezieobi, Nwosu and Mezieobi (2014) ethnic conflicts and their concomitant violence manifest in the following ways;

- Political dominance - the parameter to measure who a political leader is in Nigeria is to know the ethnic group he comes from. It does not necessarily matter whether the leader is competent or not, but the major sign post to his position is the ethnic group that produced him/her. If such an individual does not come from a favored ethnic group, he automatically losses support and loyalty from those who believe that the country belongs to them. In the struggle that attended such political leadership selection, inter ethnic conflict results.
- Formation of political parties along ethnic lines – one of the constitutional provision in Nigeria that was aimed at fanning national integration was that political parties should have membership that cut across ethnic lines. But regrettably it is observed that most political

parties in Nigeria are ethnic based. This ethnic politics that characterized party formation has continued to give rise to ethnic conflicts.

Marginalization of ethnic groups- Many ethnic groups feel that they are discriminated against, neglected, oppressed and deprived of their rights in the society. Therefore, they results to ethnic agitation, protest and often times they end up being charged by the government for in sighting violence in the society.

Hate speeches and unguided utterances – it is generally observed that many ethnic minded Nigerian leaders do not only encourage and fan ethnic conflict by their irrational utterances and actions, but they also employ conflict as political weapon to come to power and definitely stay put in power.

The arrogance of the three major ethnic groups in Nigeria, who constantly behave as if Nigeria as a nation belongs only to them without regards to other ethnic groups. This ugly trend has consistently resulted to ethnic conflict.

The Effect of Ethnic Conflicts in Nigeria

The problems associated with ethnic conflicts in Nigeria have resulted to so many dilemma in the society. The catalogue of ethnic conflicts and violence in Nigeria is profuse. Intra and inter ethnic conflicts according to Mezieobi (2014) have lead to,

Engendered irredeemable ethnic bitterness, bitter rivalry, rancor, distrust, suspicion, invidious hatred, ethnic prejudice, disharmonious co-existence, and bad blood.

Institutionalized fear of one ethnic group or the other politically dominating the others or having religious advantage over the other in terms of supremacy.

- Provoke inter and intra-ethnic attacks and reprisal attacks and killings by other ethnic groups elsewhere.
- Uncalled for destructive riots, clashes and violent activities which have gulped lives, property and huge sums of money
- In the international arena, the incessant ethnic hostilities in Nigeria, it has scared the foreign investors from doing business in Nigeria.
- Ethnic conflicts have so much implanted insecurity, socio-economic and political instability in the country that government hasn't much to offer in terms of national development.

Indices for measuring National Integration

The level and standard of national integration in every country is determined by how well such country has achieved social, political and economic integration. These tripod organs when adequately developed will results to a whole, viable and functional national integration. The following are parameter for measuring national integration in Nigeria,

Economic Integration

Economic Integration can be described as a situation where all the component aspects of an economy are brought together and aligned in such an orderly way that they work harmoniously, more effectively in a country like Nigeria (Fan, 2004). This implies that the production, distribution, transportation, communication and other economic systems are orderly organized to ensure maximum economic satisfaction in the country. Dike (2008) opined economic integration as another facet of nation building which is based on equitable distribution of wealth/resources. This means, the ability to use the resources from an area to develop other areas.

Political Integration

Political integration is described as the coming together of individuals who have decided to work as a united group to achieve whatever is their political objectives (Akinboro, 1981). He went further to emphasize that different political parties are made up individuals who dropped their personal idiosyncrasies and come together to work as a team, so as to achieve their articulated political goals. Similarly, Ebere (2005) cited in Uzoagba (2008) described the formation of political parties in Nigeria that cut across ethnic lines as raising hope for political integration. He further explained that if Nigerians would imbibe the spirit of political integration among themselves, it will foster national unity and development.

Social Integration

The issue of national integration is not a mathematical exercise of putting or bringing together the separate parts of physical elements to make a whole, rather they are experiences that involve bringing together human beings who have emotions, feelings and sentiments (Ohueri, 1995). There are bound to be conflicts and disagreements in the management of the affairs of every society. Social integration, therefore acts as an instrument that will properly channel the socialization of our youths towards good character formation, imbibing good citizenship education that will be patriotic enough to contribute in community development and nation building. This form of integration includes inter marriage activities, cultural fiesta and sporting activities.

Cultural Integration

It is clear that individuals are the units of integration. Citizens of any nation are integrated as they share a common identity. Through the

process of diffusion, elements of culture are spread by invention a new institution adopted in one place can also be adopted in neighboring areas, and in some cases continues to be adopted in adjacent point, until it may spread over the whole earth. It is clear that positive attitude and coexistence over a prolonged period of time can weld people of distinct nationality and groups together and thus create a new society out of an old one (Elaigwu, 2001) cited in Irikana, Godspower Jackson & Ibeh, (2014).

Efforts made by the Federal Government to Achieve National Integration in Nigeria

The issue of national integration cannot be overemphasized. The task of national building in a pluralist society like Nigeria is an arduous one. Owing to this fact, since the country's independence in 1960, the Nigerian leadership has made determined efforts to weld the various ethnic groups together through the following ways among others:

- In the educational sector, the government has continued to encourage the admission of students from various ethnic groups, particularly at the secondary Colleges of education and universities respectively. This programme of expansion involved the establishment of what people usually refer to as "Unity schools" in all the states of Nigeria. Recruitment into these schools is based on quota from all the states. Although these schools have been criticized and perceived as schools for the children of the elite class, it is regarded as a worthwhile effort by many people. In these schools, there is interaction and mutual understanding among students and their friendship pattern are not ethnically based.
- Establishment of the Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) it was set up to take care of admission into higher institutions of

learning. Students involvement into these institutions, particularly the universities, reflect the federal character of Nigeria.

The launching of the national Youth Service Crops in (1973). The national Youth Service Crops (NYSC) programme is designed to mobilize the young university graduates towards national integration but the unfortunate thing about it is that it focused on a small segment of the population. It concerns only university graduates who constitute only a small percentage of the Nigeria populace.

- The creation of states in the country, this is a policy that has given the minority ethnic groups a sense of belonging and has helped to shift the power base from the states to the centre. With power base tilting in favour of the centre, it is now not possible for any state to hold the entire country to ransom as happened in the past. While the creation of states is seen as a programme designed to generate an atmosphere of stability and unity among Nigerians, it has introduced a new element into the politics of Nigeria, Ohueri (1998).

In the same vein, Mezieobi (2014) described the efforts by the Government to foster national integration to include:

The Constitution of the federal Republic of Nigeria: The nation-Nigeria since 1979 does not only have a Constitution (revised in 1999) that guides and controls the behavior of individuals and all the states in Nigeria, it also encourages the entrenchment of national integration and in fact implores the constituent states to eschew inter-ethnic discrimination and sectionalism, encourage inter-ethnic co-existence and to develop 'one nationality' attitude that is positive. Invariably, the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 attaches' unbounded premium on national integration –

focusing on integrating all the 619 ethnic groups in Nigeria into one Nigeria.

- **Nigeria's National Sports Squad or Team:** Nigeria as a sovereign state in the realization of the relevance of sporting activities to engendering national unity has instituted national oriented sports teams that are open to all Nigerians irrespective of ethnic orientation or attachment. Examples of such teams are Nigeria's Super Eagles, Golden Eaglets and Falconate.
- **Uniformed Security Agents:** The Police, Navy, Air force and the infantry – Army, each wears nationally prescribed uniforms. The same is true of all paramilitary organizations such as Civil Defense Crops, Federal Road Safety crops and Traffic Wardens. Each staff composition is drawn from a national staff poll.

Factors Impeding national Integration in Nigeria

So many factors are great inhibitions to the achievement of national integration in Nigeria. In the words of Mezieobi (2014) the following among others constitute impeding factors to the realization of the goals of national integration,

1. Engrained Ethnic Consciousness

Ethnic nationality or ethnic consciousness or loyalty in Nigeria is very well represented by Mezieobi (1992 P. 206) when he quipped that “most Nigerians place their interest and those of their ethnic group before the interest of Nigeria. Everything in Nigeria has ethnic and sectional connotation or undertone.

2. The Quota System and Federal Character Principles.

These two principles which the federal government of Nigeria, as adopted panacea against ethnic imbalance in admissions of students to educational institutions and for

appointments or employment to public offices have not only compromised merit and enthroned mediocrity, qualified candidates who are sidelined by these principles and who are embittered by it, cannot visualize the promise of true national integration and cannot but stand on its way with the support of their ethnic relations who would only perceive the principles as discriminatory and holding no promise for genuine national integration.

3. The Ethnic Minority Question

There are about six hundred and nineteen (619) ethnic groups in Nigeria. The ‘big three’ ethnic groups in Nigeria which are not only recognized by the Federal Constitution of Nigeria and which languages must of necessity be studied at the Lower Basic Education Level, are the Hausa – Fulani, Igbo and Yoruba. All the other ethnic groups by implication, directly or indirectly, fall under the classification of minority ethnic groups in Nigeria and are, therefore, treated as such.

Ethnocentrism

Ethnic consciousness is not the bane to Nigeria's national integration, for ethnic diversities in Nigeria if positively harnessed would make Nigeria's ethnic integration a case for study and emulation by international communities. Nigeria's problems of national integration among other things, anchor on ethnocentrism – the tenaciously held inclination of an individual or an ethnic group to the effect that its own life ways are superior to all others that are inferior.

4. Absence of Political Leadership Will to De-ethnicize Nigeria

If ‘Nigerians are highly ethnocentric’ and the political leadership cadre is composed of people from one ethnic group or the other, it

stands to reason that the political leadership is not likely to play down on its selfish ethnic interest in the overall bid to enthrone national integration in actuality. Political leadership in Nigeria lacks the political will to entrench national integration in Nigeria and, therefore, lay to rest the total commitment to the pursuit of national integration which has constituted itself into a detractor factors of governments in Nigeria to good governance.

Role of Culture and ethnicity in Promoting National Integration in Nigeria

Every ethnic group has their own culture which if properly shared and respected will promote oneness which is national integration. The following, among others are ways through which culture and ethnicity can promote national integration:-

- **Cultural Universality:** is a general practice found in every society, it includes marriage, sports, cooking and sexual restrictions. These general cultural practices if properly harnessed eg, inter-ethnic marriages which can enhance understanding among different groups, cultural learnability, tolerance, respect for other peoples culture, can facilitate and promote national integration among citizens of a particular country.
- **Cultural Learnability** – Is a process of social interaction within a socio-cultural milieu. When citizens learn the cultures of different ethnic groups in any given country, it promotes love, understanding and tolerances among the citizens and their by enhance national integration.
- **Cultural Diffusion** - Is the spread of cultural items from one ethnic group to the other. In a country like Nigeria, cultural diffusion has fostered unity, love, accommodation and

tolerances among different ethnic groups which thereby facilitate national integration.

• **Cultural Sharing** – Is not a personal affair, rather it is a societal issues that enables members of a given society to respect the dominate culture and make them to guide and regulate their actions and behavior in the society. Cultural sharing allows citizens of a given society to learn, appreciate, and promote the interest of each other.

Conclusion

Culture and ethnicity are two important factors that influence national integration in a multi-ethnic, multi-cultural and multi-lingual state. The desire for a truly united and integrated society where citizens irrespective of their ethnic, cultural, religious, economic, educational and social background have rights to equal and opportunity to benefit from the affairs of the government, is uppermost in Nigeria's scheme of things. To achieve the above, Nigeria has to overcome the challenges posed by ethnic consciousness and cultural differences and provide favourable socio-economic and political climate that will lead to a significant reduction of imbalance in socio-economic and political gaps among the various ethnic groups. This, no doubt, will bring about social, economic, political, religious, educational cooperation among the various ethnic nationalities in Nigeria and reduce ethnic tensions and cultural bias which are the bane of national integration.

Recommendations

The following among others are recommended as measure to achieve and sustain national integration amid ethnic and cultural differences in Nigeria.

- Nigeria should see their ethnic and cultural pluralism as a blessing and not a problem and

therefore emphasize on those things that unite and bind us together and de-emphasize on the things that divide us.

- There is the need for good governance with effective democratization process to manage ethnicity and variegated cultural values thereby aiding national integration.
- The government should sincerely and effectively adopt federal character as an equitable principle in the distribution of resources, amenities and political appointments.
- Government at all levels should put an end to discriminatory practices in government appointments and discourage winner takes all syndrome to avoid over heating the polity.
- There is the urgent need for the restructuring of the federation. The present over centralized federal structure with much power concentrating on the centre should be restructured. More powers and resources should be given to constituent unity so that they can develop on their own and at their own pace.

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